

A Comparative Study of State Anxiety Levels Among Cricket Players of Different Age Groups

Amrit Kumar Mahato¹, Mahesh Sawata Khetmalis².

¹Research Scholar, ²Associate Professor

Department of Physical Education and Sport Science
Visva-Bharati, (Central University)
Santiniketan-731235

Abstract:-

Background: Anxiety is a state of mind. In cricket, the batsman, bowlers, and fielders experience state anxiety, particularly in the time of match situation.

Aim: To observe the level of state anxiety among different age groups of male cricketers before a match situation.

Method: Subjects - 44 male cricket players were voluntarily participating in this study. The age range of the subjects was i.16-17 ii.18-19 iii. 20-21 iv. 22-23 years. In each age group, 11 subjects were selected from Birbhum district, West Bengal, India.

Measurement tools: State anxiety has been evaluated through the manual for 'Anxiety Scale' developed by Subhash Sarkar and Goutam Das (ISBN:93-88616-28-9). The anxiety has been subdivided into six items i. worry ii. general anxiety iii. low self-confidence iv. overthinking v. panic attacks vi. depression.

Design: The subjects filled up a questionnaire 30 minutes before the match. The data were analyzed statistically.

Findings: The age group of 22-23 years cricketers was found to have a comparatively high mean score in all the anxiety parameters compared to the others groups, indicating this group feels more state anxiety.

Conclusion: State anxiety level has been found to be higher in the senior cricketer group.

Keyword:- State Anxiety; Cricket Players.

I. INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is described as an unpleasant emotional condition that can happen in potentially dangerous situations and heighten anxiety and self-doubt, frequently resulting in a decline in performance. In the literature, there has been a lot of discussion about the link between worry and poor performance. (Runswick et al., 2018) Sports psychology is a science in which the principles of psychology are applied in a sports or exercise setting. These principles are often used to enhance performance. The sport psychologist is interested in helping every sport participant reach his or her potential as an athlete. If helping a young athlete develops self-control and confidence results in superior athletic performance. (K.S et al., 2015) We know that in a country like India, where cricket is a very popular team sport, and it is mainly played by people of all ages watching the game as well as the game and even our children should watch cricket and have the

feeling of taking it as a career. Anxiety before or during a cricket match can hinder a cricket player's performance as an athlete. The coordinated movement required by a cricket match becomes increasingly difficult when the body is tense. Some level of physical arousal is helpful and prepares us for competition. But when the physical symptoms of anxiety are too great, they may seriously interfere with a player's ability to compete. Similarly, decide how much to worry about how they perform in a match, but severe symptoms of anxiety, such as negative thinking patterns and anticipation of failure, can bring self-fulfilling predictions (Mane, 2021). Generally, there are two types of anxiety: state anxiety and trait anxiety. State anxiety involves a feeling of apprehension, tension, fear, and an increase in physiological arousal. This is an immediate emotional state response to the specific situation. State anxiety also consists of somatic and cognitive anxiety. (Kar, 2013) Somatic anxiety is closely related to physiological aspects of anxiety, which involve physical symptoms such as rapid heartbeat, shortness of breath, and muscular. (Martinent et al., 2010) Another component of state anxiety is cognitive anxiety which refers to worry and emotional distress for upcoming events (Filaire et al., 2001). Trait anxiety, which is involved an experience of anxiety over a long period of time toward stressful environments (Kornspan, 2012)

➤ Aim of the study

To observe the level of state anxiety among different age groups of male cricketers before a match situation.

➤ Objectives:

- To find out the status and comparison of worry on different age level cricket players.
- To find out the group and compare general anxiety on different age level cricket players.
- To find out the status and comparison of low self-confidence on different age level cricket players.
- To find out the group and comparison of overthinking on different age level cricket players.
- To determine the status and comparison of panic attacks on different age-level cricket players.
- To find out the group and compare depression on different age level cricket players.
- To find out the status and comparison of state anxiety on different age-level cricket players

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ Selection of Subjects

For the purpose of the study 44 male club-level cricket players aged between 16 to 23 years were selected from Birbhum, WB, India. The age group of the subjects were 16 to 17 years, 18 to 19 years, 20 to 21 years, and 22 to 23 years.

➤ Selection of Variables

Keeping the feasibility criterion in mind, the static anxiety variable was selected for the present study. Variables were a worry, general anxiety, self-confidence, overthinking, panic attacks, and Depression.

➤ Criterion Measures

State Anxiety will be assessed with the help of anxiety scale developed by Subhash Sarkar and Goutam Das.

• Procedure

Before administering the questionnaire, the rules and process for filling up the questionnaire are clearly explained by the researcher before the selected subjects so as to the most reliable information collected from the subjects for the purpose of the study.

• Scoring

Scoring is done on Likert 4-point scale, i.e., 4 is always, 3 is mostly, 2 is sometimes, 1 is rarely.

➤ Statistical Procedure:

To assess the level of state anxiety among cricket players from different age groups, Descriptive Statistics, i.e. (Mean, Standard Deviation) was used.

To compare the state anxiety among cricket players from age groups, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used.

III. DISCUSSION & FINDINGS

Table: 1 Consolidated Table of State Anxiety on Different Age-Level Cricket Players

Sl.	State Anxiety Age Group	Mean				Sd				F	F crit	Significant
		16-17	18-19	20-21	22-23	16-17	18-19	20-21	22-23			
1	worry	14.91	12.64	15.36	16.73	2.84	3.17	2.77	3.04	2.8	2.86	Not Significant
2	General anxiety	16.64	16	16.55	17.18	2.54	1.79	2.54	2.6	0.58	2.86	Not Significant
3	self-confidence	16.27	16.82	15.18	17.36	2.33	3.84	2.93	1.63	0.85	2.86	Not-Significant
4	Over thinking	16.27	15.64	14.82	17.18	4	2.8	3.84	2.89	1.02	2.86	Not-Significant
5	Panic attack	18	16.36	16.55	16.18	5.2	2.77	2.25	3.06	0.48	2.86	Not-Significant
6	Depression	13.91	13.55	16.27	14	3.36	3.21	1.56	2.9	2.19	2.86	Not-Significant
7	State Anxiety	96	91	95.36	98.64	14.07	12.32	10.45	11.03	0.61	2.86	Not-Significant

- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of worry on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are 14.91 ± 2.84 , 12.64 ± 3.17 , 15.36 ± 2.77 , 16.73 ± 3.04 respectively. Fig. 1 shows the mean score of Worry on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where the 22-23 age group had a higher mean score than the other age group. Consolidated table-1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference in worry among different age-level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained F ratio was 2.81, which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.
- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of general anxiety on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are 16.64 ± 2.54 , 16 ± 1.79 , 16.55 ± 2.54 , 17.18 ± 2.60 respectively. Fig. 2 shows the mean score of general anxiety on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where 22-23 age group had a higher mean score as compared to the other age group. Consolidated table 1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference in general anxiety among different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was .58 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.
- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of low self-confidence in different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are 16.27 ± 2.33 , 16.82 ± 3.84 , 15.18 ± 2.93 , 17.36 ± 1.63 respectively. Fig. 3 shows the mean score of low self-confidence on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where the 22-23 age group had a higher mean score than the other age group. Consolidated table-1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference in low self-confidence among different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was .85 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.

- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of overthinking on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are $16.27 \pm 4.00, 15.64 \pm 2.80, 14.82 \pm 3.84, 17.18 \pm 2.89$ respectively. Fig. 4 showed the mean score of overthinking on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where 22-23 age group had higher mean score as compared to the others age group. Consolidated table- 1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference in thinking on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was 1.02 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.
- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of panic attacks on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are $18 \pm 5.20, 16.36 \pm 2.77, 16.55 \pm 2.25, 16.18 \pm 3.06$ respectively. Fig. 5 shows the mean score of Panic attack on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where 16-17 age group had a higher mean score as compared to the others age group. Consolidated table- 1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference of panic attacks among different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was .48 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.
- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of depression on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are $13.91 \pm 3.36, 13.55 \pm 3.21, 16.27 \pm 1.56, 14 \pm 2.90$ respectively. Fig. 6 showed the mean score of depression on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where 20-21 age group had higher mean score as compared to the others age group. Consolidated table- 1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference of depression on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was 2.19 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.
- From the above-consolidated table no.1, it has been found that the mean and SD of static anxiety on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) are $96 \pm 14.07, 91 \pm 12.32, 95.36 \pm 10.45, 98.64 \pm 11.03$ respectively. Fig. 7 shows the mean score of state anxiety on Different Age Level Cricket Players, where the 22-23 age group had a higher mean score as compared to the others age group. Consolidated table-1 revealed that there was an insignificant difference of state anxiety on different age level cricket players (Age group 16-17, Age group 18-19, Age group 20-21, Age group 22-23) as obtained f ratio was .60 which was less than the tabulated value of 2.86 at 0.05 level of significance.

IV. CONCLUSION

- In conclusion, results related to the general psychological perspective of the cricket player reveal that most cricketers are aware of the role of the psychology behind the successful performance. Still, they don't have sufficient opportunities to involve with the anxiety training session. The coaches also have a moderate knowledge of psychology but do not impart that knowledge to their trainees. So, there is a lack of anxiety training compared to physical training.
- The comparison of the mean of the four groups indicated that the mean state anxiety level of the 22-23 aged cricket players were found to have a comparatively higher mean score as compared to the other cricket players, which indicates that 22-23 aged cricket players feel more state anxiety as compare to other cricket players.
- In the present study, no statistically significant differences have been observed between the four. Group cricket players. This may be due to a marginal age difference.
- The observations may be due to the conduct of similar practices and training sessions.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Runswick, O. R., Roca, A., Williams, A. M., Bezodis, N. E., & North, J. S. (2018). The effects of anxiety and situation-specific context on perceptual–motor skill: a multi-level investigation. *Psychological Research*, 82(4), 708–719. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-017-0856-8>
- [2]. Filaire, E., Sagnol, M., Ferrand, C., Maso, F., & Lac, G. (2001). Psychophysiological stress in judo athletes during competitions. *The Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness*, 41(2), 263–268.
- [3]. Kar, D. S. (2013). *Measurement of Competition Level Anxiety of College Level Athletes by Using SCAT*. 2(3).
- [4]. Kornspan, A. S. (2012). History of sport and performance psychology. In *The Oxford handbook of sport and performance psychology* (pp. 3–23). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199731763.013.0001>
- [5]. K.S, Dr. R., Guruprasad, S., & BhaviGhelani. (2015). Assessment of Anxiety in Sports Person Pre & Post Sports Performance A Study on: Levels of Anxiety in Individual Vs Group Sport. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 4, 8901. <https://doi.org/10.15680/IJIRSET.2015.0409085>
- [6]. Mane, M. (2021). *A Comparative study of pre-competition Anxiety Level between Cricket Batsman and Fast Bowlers of University of Mumbai*. 118.
- [7]. Martinent, G., Ferrand, C., Guillet, E., & Gauthier, S. (2010). Validation of the French version of the Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 Revised (CSAI-2R) including frequency and direction scales. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 11(1), 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2009.05.001>

- [8]. India's Largest House of Psychological Tests | Seller and distributor of Psychological Books | National Psychological Corportaiou. (n.d.). Retrieved February 22, 2023, from <https://www.npcindia.com/Psychological-Test/ANXIETY-SCALE/1000182/1>